

MINIMUM WEIGHT DESIGN OF A COMPOSITE MATERIAL SAFETY WHEEL SUBJECT TO STRENGTH, STIFFNESS AND IMPACT CONSTRAINTS

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ABSTRACT

In the transportation of goods via road, it is not uncommon for a blowout to occur on one of the wheels of a rig. If such a blowout were to occur on a front wheel at high speed, the results could be disastrous. One way of safeguarding against such a mishap is to use a safety wheel on the outside of the existing wheel. A wheel constructed from composite materials could be lighter and stronger than one constructed from conventional materials. A design study of such a wheel is presented here.

INTRODUCTION

The typical operating conditions of a wheel are simulated with a computer model. The magnitude and locations of the maximum stresses in the structure can then be determined. A wheel constructed from conventional materials would be heavy and possibly require holes to reduce its weight, also reducing the strength. It was assumed from the outset that the composite design would not require any weight reduction methods such as this. The resulting design would thus be simple to construct and would not have problems of stress concentration around the holes in the structure.

Carbon, kevlar and glass fiber composites are investigated as possible materials for the wheel. Various combinations of these materials are also investigated to try and achieve the most desirable properties of each material. The stiffness, strength, weight and cost are affected by the composition of the materials chosen and by the fiber volume content

of the material.

Several geometric models are generated, each using the same composite material of the same thickness. Static analysis is used to simulate the real-life loading conditions on each model. The criteria that are investigated are peak stress and maximum deflection in each geometric model. The finite element method is used for this purpose.

The final design is a combination of the most desirable material with the best geometric model to suit those material properties. The cost versus the weight, strength and stiffness of each geometric model with varying material combinations is presented with a view towards determining the optimum combination of weight and cost. There are many factors which affect the composite strength, making a precise estimate of the strength difficult. In particular, it is difficult to predict the behaviour of a composite under impact. As discussed in [1] and [2], the classical plate theory tends to predict results that are greatly overstiff. The impact strength of a composite material is very difficult to predict. Considerable work has been carried out in this field as summarized in [3]. Large variations in material properties can also occur. These difficulties are generally overcome by adopting a suitable safety factor. Some approximate material properties were determined from calculations and by comparing with published test data [4].

Several geometric models were generated, each using the same composite material of the same thickness. The models were compared under identical loading conditions to determine the most suitable model. Carbon and glass fiber composites were investigated as possible materials for the wheel. The strength, stiffness and cost of various combinations of glass and carbon with different fiber volume contents were compared in an attempt to find the most cost efficient material. The maximum thickness of wheel that can be accommodated is 8 mm. As will be shown later, the thickness of the wheel depends on the material chosen.

GEOMETRIC AND MATERIAL MODELING

MODELING OF WHEEL DESIGNS

A point load of 3750 kg was located on the bottom of the wheel to simulate contact with the road surface. Note that only half the wheel needed to be modeled (Fig. 1). The other half could be taken into account by symmetry boundary conditions. The force applied to the bottom of the model was thus: $F = \frac{L_{frontaxle}}{4} \times g$

COMPOSITE MATERIAL PROPERTIES AND COST

Due to the uncertainty on the exact fiber volume content and data on material properties

for each fiber volume content, it was difficult to determine the exact values for Young's modulus and ultimate stress for each combination. However, the material properties were calculated and compared with published experimental results [4] to determine as closely as possible their expected values. It was decided that kevlar would not be considered in the design due to its poor properties under compressive loading. On the other hand, the high strength and stiffness of carbon fiber composites under both tensile and compressive loading make them very suitable for this application. However carbon fiber composites are extremely expensive. The cost of carbon fibres is up to 50 times that of the equivalent glass fibres. A combination of glass and carbon in the construction of the wheel gives high strength and stiffness with a cost that is not excessively high.

Tables 1 and 2 give the density and Young's modulus of various combinations of glass and carbon in a matrix of Derekane 411-45 resin. Derekane 411 is a vinyl ester resin in common industrial use. From [4], the following data is obtained:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \rho_{\text{carbon}} (T - 300) & = & 1.77 \text{ g/cm}^3 & E_{\text{carbon}} & = & 231 \text{ GPa} \\
 \rho_{\text{glass}} (E - \text{glass}) & = & 2.55 \text{ g/cm}^3 & E_{\text{glass}} & = & 72 \text{ GPa} \\
 \rho_{\text{resin}} (\text{Derekane 411}) & = & 1.12 \text{ g/cm}^3 & E_{\text{resin}} & = & 3.3 \text{ GPa} \\
 \sigma_{\text{u-carbon}} & = & 3240 \text{ GPa} & C_{\text{carbon}} & = & 360.00 \text{ R/kg} \\
 \sigma_{\text{u-glass}} & = & 3100 \text{ GPa} & C_{\text{glass}} & = & 6.00 \text{ R/kg} \\
 \sigma_{\text{u-resin}} & = & 81 \text{ GPa} & C_{\text{resin}} & = & 17.00 \text{ R/kg}
 \end{array}$$

where R is the symbol for the South African Rand. By the rule of mixtures:

$$\rho_{\text{composite}} = \rho_{\text{carbon}} V_{\text{carbon}} + \rho_{\text{glass}} V_{\text{glass}} + \rho_{\text{resin}} V_{\text{resin}} \tag{1}$$

and

$$E_{\text{composite}} = E_{\text{carbon}} V_{\text{carbon}} + E_{\text{glass}} V_{\text{glass}} + E_{\text{resin}} V_{\text{resin}} \tag{2}$$

It is assumed some form of bidirectional weave pattern will be used for the construction of the wheel. In this case, only half the fibres can be expected to contribute their full strength and rigidity to withstand a given load. The behaviour of a composite material is more complicated than assumed here and prompted the work presented in [5] and [6]. For design purposes with a suitable safety factor, the results obtained using this principle compare favorably with those of [4]. For various other combinations of glass, carbon and resin, the density and Young's modulus are shown in Tables 1 and 2. The

Table 1: Density (g/cm^3)

$V_f(\%)$	0% Carbon	25% Carbon	50% Carbon	75% Carbon	100% Carbon
40	1.692	1.614	1.536	1.458	1.38
50	1.835	1.738	1.64	1.543	1.45
60	1.978	1.861	1.744	1.627	1.51

Table 2: Young's Modulus (GPa)

$V_f(\%)$	0% Carbon	25% Carbon	50% Carbon	75% Carbon	100% Carbon
40	16.38	24.33	32.28	40.23	48.18
50	19.65	29.59	39.53	49.46	59.4
60	22.92	34.85	46.77	58.7	70.62

ultimate strength of a composite material depends on the type of fibres used. After studying the results of tests presented in [4], it can be seen that carbon is stronger than glass but in a composite fails at approximately 1% elongation. Glass fails at approximately 1.6% elongation. Carbon is equally strong in tension and compression whereas glass is typically weaker under compression than tension. Taking the elongation at composite failure to be 1% regardless of the composition produced results which compared favorably with those presented in [4]. Consider the case where the fiber volume content is 50% and there are equal quantities (by volume) of carbon and glass. The strength of the composite is then:

$$\sigma_{ult} = E_{composite} \epsilon_{max} \quad (3)$$

The values of ultimate strength for various other combinations were calculated and are shown in Table 3. The cost of the composite used in construction is important. This can

Table 3: Ultimate Strength Based on Data from [4] (MPa)

$V_f(\%)$	0% Carbon	25% Carbon	50% Carbon	75% Carbon	100% Carbon
40	164	243	323	402	482
50	197	296	395	495	594
60	229	348	468	587	706

be best described as specific cost (R/kg). For the same material composition considered above, the specific cost is:

$$C_{composite} = \frac{C_c \rho_c V_c + C_g \rho_g V_g + C_r \rho_r V_r}{\rho_{composite}} \quad (4)$$

For other material combinations, the specific costs are shown in Table 4. The total cost of the wheel can be calculated from the specific cost in the following way:

$$C_{total} = C_{composite} \times \rho_{composite} \times V_{wheel} \quad (5)$$

For a wheel thickness of 8 mm the volume of the wheel is $5.0652 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^3$. For a wheel made with other combinations of the component materials, the thickness of the material to be used can be calculated according to the strength of the material in question. For instance, the required thickness of a wheel made from 40% glass and 60%

Table 4: Specific Cost (R/kg)

$V_f(\%)$	0% Carbon	25% Carbon	50% Carbon	75% Carbon	100% Carbon
40	10.4	49.4	92.4	140.0	193.0
50	9.4	54.6	105.3	162.3	226.3
60	8.5	59.15	116.6	182.3	258.2

Table 5: Final Cost Corrected for Strength (R)

$V_f(\%)$	0% Carbon	25% Carbon	50% Carbon	75% Carbon	100% Carbon
40	254	778	1042	1204	1309
50	208	760	1036	1199	1309
60	174	750	1030	1198	1309

resin (0% carbon) would be $t = 22.8 \text{ mm}$.

The volume of a wheel made from this material would also be altered in the same way. From Eqn (5), the costs of a wheel made from various different combinations of constituent materials are given in Table 5. Table 5 takes into account that some combinations are stronger than others and gives an indication of how increased strength can compensate for the increased cost to a certain extent. The cheapest material configuration is 60% glass fibres and 40% resin by volume. The thickness of a wheel made from this material would be 16.3 mm . This is thicker than the limit of 8 mm . The cheapest material to yield a thickness 8 mm is that composed of 30% carbon, 30% glass and 40% resin by volume.

GEOMETRIC MODELING OF COMPOSITE WHEEL

Four computer models of different wheel geometries were generated. The material assumed for the construction was 8mm thick and consisted of 60% fiber volume content with equal volumes of glass and carbon fibres. The resin properties were assumed to be those of Derekane 411. Fig. 1 shows the first wheel model generated. The center of the wheel has a steel reinforcing disk in place around the hub and stud holes. This disk reduces stress concentration around the stud holes and also provides protection for the composite material against abrasion from the nuts as they are tightened onto the studs. Stresses are lower than 200 MPa . The safety factor on the design is thus approximately 2.3. It is important to have a safety factor such as this. There are several tight junctures which tend to reduce the effective material strength. The effect of material strength reduction is discussed in [7]. It is also shown in [7] that the finite element analysis tends to overestimate the strength of a composite structure.

Fig. 2 shows a modification of the original composite design with 5 "spokes" to stiffen

the wheel. The material is the same 60% fiber volume content made up from equal amounts of glass and carbon. The thickness of the laminate in this model is also 8mm. The material cost of constructing such a wheel would not be much greater than a solid disk. However, the outer lip will have to be made in an additional molding process which will add to the complication of constructing the wheel. Fig. 3 shows the modification of the original composite design taken one step further. The model is a 10-spoke wheel under the same loading conditions as before.

RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the finite element model used for analysis of the wheel with no "spokes". Table 6 summarizes the results of all the models. Note that the peak Von Mises stress in the model shown in Fig. 1 occurs in the outermost "layer" of the wheel, layer 1. This "layer" of the wheel includes the steel reinforcing ring around the stud holes of the structure and the outer 4 mm of composite material. The other "layer" of material which does not have reinforcement is the inner 4mm of the composite material including the material which forms the backing for the steel reinforcing ring. The stresses are higher in the layer with the steel ring since the stiffness of the steel is higher than that of the composite material. The steel thus takes more of the load. The peak displacement is large (12.4 mm). This is to be expected, however, since the composite material considered has a low Young's modulus.

The finite element model of a 5-spoke composite wheel constructed from the same material and under the same loading is shown in Fig. 2. Note that the peak stresses are lower than for the non-spoked wheel, although the peak displacement does not change greatly.

Fig. 3 shows the model for a 10-spoke wheel. Again the stresses are lower than that of a 5-spoke wheel, but the displacement of the wheel under loading remains high.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Tables 1 to 5 list the material properties of various combinations of glass and carbon. The cheapest material has the one of the worst sets of material properties, requiring an unrealistically thick material section. The optimum choice of material is by volume: 30% carbon, 30% glass and 40% resin. The material cost of the wheel would total approximately R1030. Another consideration is that as the fiber volume content of the material is changed, the method of manufacture will most likely also change. The cheapest form of construction is a standard hand layup. As the fiber volume content

is increased, increased pressure must be applied to the wheel while it is in the mold to ensure there are no voids or weak areas in the structure.

The desired geometry of the wheel was also be selected. There were several choices here:

1. **Type of steel reinforcement around stud holes.** Either a steel reinforcing ring could be used or steel inserts could be located around the stud holes. The continuous ring was chosen as it yields lower stresses and is also more easily located on the wheel.
2. **Geometric shape of wheel.** The simplest wheel shape is the non-spoked design. This layout would be the cheapest to construct. The 5-spoke wheel would most likely provide greater rigidity, particularly for loads under cornering. It would, however be more difficult to construct. The construction would have to take place in two phases. The first phase would be to mold the inner region of the wheel including the "spokes" and the steel reinforcing ring. The second phase would be to mold the outer lip of the wheel. This method of construction will be more costly and more time consuming than that of the non-spoked design. The 10-spoke design yields the lowest stresses and would most likely have the greatest rigidity under cornering loads. The construction of this wheel would cost approximately the same as the 5-spoke wheel. It should be noted that the 10-spoke wheel would almost certainly be the safest design, particularly because of its superior cornering performance. The choice for the best general layout of the wheel is therefore a 10-spoked design.

SELECTED DESIGN

The final choice for the optimum wheel design is a wheel constructed for an 8 mm thick layup of composite material consisting of 30% carbon, 30% glass and 40% Derekan 411-45 resin. The geometric layout chosen is a 10-spoke wheel with a steel reinforcing ring around the holes for the wheel studs.

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Figure 1: Finite element model of non-spoked wheel

Figure 2: Model of 5-spoke wheel

Figure 3: Model of 10-spoke wheel

Table 6: Summary of Finite Element Results

	Non-Spoked	5-spoke	10-spoke
σ_{max} (MPa) Layer 1	199	180	162
σ_{max} (MPa) Layer 2	194	187	153
Displacement (mm)	12.4	13.0	12.9